

Table S3: The information of PDB templates for 3D protein modeling

TMEM proteins	PDB template	Description	Sequence Identity	Coverage
GbTMEM214-4_D	5f0n.1.A	cohesin subunit Pds5	15.34%	295-490
GbTMEM214-4_A	6whb.1.A	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 1	13.04%	320-459
GbTMEM214-1_D	6whb.1.A	Mitogen-activated protein kinase kinase kinase 1	11.68%	314-452
GbTMEM214-1_A	3tj1.1.A	RNA polymerase I-specific transcription initiation factor RRN3	10.91%	197-342
GbTMEM214-7_D	6epf.1.S	26S proteasome non-ATPase regulatory subunit 2	13.24%	57-127
GbTMEM214-7_A	6tnf.1.B	Fanconi anemia complementation group I	17.31%	256-439